

Hexacoordinated Mixed-ligand Complexes of Vanadium(IV) and Copper(II)

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The literature reports simple complexes of metal ions with Schiff bases derived from amino acids¹. But their mixed-ligand complexes are very rare. Keeping this fact in mind, we have prepared some new mixed ligand complexes of V^{IV} and Cu^{II} with tridentate Schiff bases derived from glycine, salicylaldehyde and amino bases, e.g. quinoline (Q), isoquinoline (IQ), 2-picoline (2-pic), 4-picoline (4-pic) and pyridine (Py).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data and conductivity of the complexes are tabulated in Table 1. All the complexes are soluble in DMSO but insoluble in H₂O. The molar conductance values of all the complexes (16.32–18.36 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) indicated that the complexes are non-electrolyte². The results are consistent with the octahedral structure of the V^{IV} and Cu^{II} complexes.

The observed values of effective magnetic moments at room temperature are given in Table 1. The magnetic moments of the V^{IV} complexes (1.66–1.77 B.M.) indicate the presence of the one unpaired electron and octahedral stereochemistry of the complexes³. The magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} complexes (1.76–1.77 B.M.) also indicate the octahedral in nature³.

The electronic spectra (nujol) of the oxovanadium (IV) complexes revealed four bands at 17 000–17 416, 22 350–23 450, 32 573–33 320 and 38 950–39 420 cm⁻¹ indicating the transitions ²B₂ → ²B₁ (B₂ → B₁⁺) and ²B₂ → ²A₁ (b₂ → a^{*}) and the latter two for the charge transfer bands. The copper(II) complexes showed three bands at 13 900–14 316, 15 500–16 000 and 17 000–17 700 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transition from τ², xy, xz and yz to x² - y² respectively. All these bands are typical for octahedral complexes^{4,5}.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Mol. formula)	Decomp. temp. (°C)/ (Colour)	Analysis % . Found/(Calcd.)			
		M	C	N	H
[VO(SB)(IQ) ₃] (C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ V)	122 (Grey)	10.43 (10.33)	66.40 66.38	8.60 8.54	4.30 4.28
[VO(SB)(4-pic) ₂] (C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ V)	220–222 (Grey)	11.84 (11.73)	58.62 58.59	9.76 9.61	4.88 4.84
[VO(SB)(Py) ₂] (C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ V)	138 (Grey)	12.67 (12.69)	56.72 56.74	10.44 10.09	4.22 4.10
[VO(SB)(2-pic) ₂] (C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ V)	221 (Grey)	18.84 (18.81)	58.62 58.50	9.70 9.63	4.88 4.47
[VO(SB)(Q) ₂] (C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ V)	130 ^a (Grey)	10.43 (9.87)	66.40 66.30	8.60 8.54	4.30 4.15
[Cu(SB)(Q) ₃] (C ₃₆ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cu)	124–126 (Green)	10.12 (10.15)	68.84 68.91	8.92 8.91	4.46 4.47
[Cu(SB)(IQ) ₃] (C ₃₆ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cu)	139 ^a (Green)	10.12 (10.13)	68.84 68.78	8.92 8.83	4.46 4.51
[Cu(SB)(Py) ₃] (C ₃₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₃ Cu)	139 (Green)	13.32 (13.09)	60.36 60.58	11.74 11.71	4.61 4.63
[Cu(SB)(2-pic) ₃] (C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cu)	189 (Green)	12.23 (12.13)	62.36 60.39	10.77 10.70	5.39 5.43
[Cu(SB)(4-pic) ₃] (C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cu)	209 (Green)	12.23 (12.09)	62.36 60.31	10.77 10.69	5.39 5.07

^aM.p., °C.

The strong ir bands at 1 630 (C=N), 3 400 (OH) and 1 420 cm⁻¹ (C-O) in the spectra of the free Schiff bases shifted to ~1 600, 3 390–3 410 and 1 290–1 375 cm⁻¹ respectively, in the spectra of the complexes, indicating the coordination of Schiff bases with the metals. The characteristic ring vibration of the cyclic

amines at $1400\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ generally shows significant changes on complexation⁶. But in the present complexes these bands could not be distinguished because of the overlapping of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ bands. The in-plane and out-of-plane ring deformation modes of the heterocyclic amines observed at ~ 610 and $\sim 420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, shifted to higher frequencies, confirming their coordination through nitrogen. The presence of M–O and M–N bonding of the complexes are evident from the appearance of bands at ~ 600 and $\sim 500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

¹H nmr spectra of the complexes [VO(SB)(IQ)₂] showed two singlet for C₆H₄ and CH₂ at $\delta 7.5$ and 2.6 respectively. A multiplet was obtained for the Schiff base for C₆H₄ and a singlet for CH at $\delta 7.2$ and 6.7 respectively. Complex of the type [VO(SB)(4-pic)₂] showed peaks at $\delta 1.2$ and 7.5 for CH₃ and C₅H₄ ring respectively. A singlet $\delta 2.6$ and a multiplet at $\delta 7.8$ were obtained for CH₂ and C₆H₄ (Schiff base) respectively. [Cu(SB)(Q)₃] complex showed resonance at $\delta 2.5$ (s, CH₂), 7.4 (m, C₄H₄), 7.8 due to (m, C₆H₄) and 3.6 . [Cu(SB)(IQ)₃] complex showed resonance at $\delta 2.7$ (CH₂), 3.6 (=CH) and 7.6 (m, C₄H₄). Two different multiplets were also obtained ($\delta 7.8$ ppm) for three isoquinoline rings. Presence of all the groups surrounding the metal atom indicates the coordination and also the octahedral geometry of the complexes.

Experimental

Conductivity was measured at room temperature in suitable solvents using a WPA CM-35 conductivity meter and dip-type cell with platinised electrode. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on an Ultrospec K-4053 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a XL GEM-200 instrument. The solid state magnetic moments was measured by the Gouy method on a Sherwood balance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as a calibrant; diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants. An electrothermal apparatus was used for the determination of melting or decomposition point. The metals were determined by the literature procedure⁵.

All the chemicals were used of reagent grade. Copper(II) chloride, vanadium(IV) chloride, quinoline, 412

isoquinoline, 2-picoline, 4-picoline, pyridine, glycine, salicylaldehyde and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) (all E. Merck) were used.

Preparation of Schiff base : To glycine (0.01 mol) dissolved in water (20 ml), a solution of *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in 95% ethanol (30 ml) was added dropwise. The mixture was then refluxed on a water-bath at about 80° for 3–4 h. The colour of the solution became yellow. After drying the solution the decomposition temperature of the resulting solid was found to be 226–230°.

Preparation of complexes : The metal chloride (0.01 mol) was added dropwise to a solution of the Schiff base solution (20 ml; 0.01 mol) and then 95% ethanolic solution (45 ml) of the heterocyclic base (0.02 or 0.03 mol) was mixed dropwise at 50°. The resulting solid was washed successively with water, ethanol, and ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over silica gel. The complexes were isolated in pure state as monitored by tlc.

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